

Studies in Copper(II) Chelates. Part-X. Mixed Chelates with Tridentate Iminodiacetate and a Bidentate α, α' -dipyridyl, *o*-Phenanthroline or Biguanide

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Three new mixed chelates of copper(II) with a tridentate iminodiacetate anion (IDA) and a bidentate α, α' -dipyridyl (dipy), *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) or biguanide (BigH) have been prepared and characterised: $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. They are non-conducting in water and show normal magnetic moments. Infrared and electronic spectra have been discussed. A distorted octahedral stereochemistry with $[\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_3]$ chromophore is suggested for all the chelates.

MIXED ligand complexes of copper(II)^{1,2} and oxo-vanadium(IV)³ containing a tridentate dibasic Schiff base and a bidentate dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) have been reported. We now report three new mixed chelates of copper(II): $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Formation constants of some mixed complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{IDA})(\text{L})]$ (L = glycine⁴, alanine⁴, pyridine⁵ etc.) have recently been reported.

Experimental

Bis(biguanide) copper(II) chloride dihydrate was prepared by standard method⁶.

Preparation of the mixed chelates: $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Method A: Iminodiacetic acid (.001 mole in 10 ml water) was added to copper(II) acetate dihydrate (.001 mole in 20 ml ethanol) when the colour changed from green to deep blue. The solution was treated with dipyridyl (.001 mole in 10 ml ethanol), concentrated (20 ml) and kept in a refrigerator. The blue crystals were purified from hot water and dried in air.

Method B: Dipyridyl (.001 mole in 10 ml ethanol) was added to a solution of copper acetate (.001 mole in 20 ml hot ethanol) when a deep blue solution was obtained. To this iminodiacetic acid (.001 mole in 20 ml hot water) was added and the whole solution was concentrated (20-25 ml), cooled in a refrigerator and treated as above.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Obtained as above using *o*-phenanthroline instead of dipyridyl.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

Method A: Bis(biguanide) copper(II) chloride dihydrate (.001 mole) was dissolved in hot water (20 ml) and converted to deep blue mono(biguanide) copper(II) chloride by adding dilute hydrochloric acid (pH 4). To this solution iminodiacetic acid (.001 mole in 10 ml hot water) was added. The solution was then concentrated (10-15 ml) and cooled in a refrigerator when a blue compound with a pale violet tinge separated out. The compound was recrystallised from hot water.

Method B: Iminodiacetic acid (.001 mole in 30 ml hot water) was added to a solution of copper(II) acetate dihydrate (.001 mole in 20 ml hot ethanol) when a deep blue solution was obtained. This solution was then neutralised by adding dilute ammonia solution. To this biguanide hydrochloride (.001 mole, 30 ml of water) was added and the solution worked up as above.

Reaction of the mixed chelates: Ammonium thiocyanate reacts with $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{IDA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to precipitate quantitatively green coloured $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{SCN})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{SCN})_2]$. Estimation of the copper content of the preparations via method B was done by weighing the insoluble thiocyanate complexes⁷.

Analysis: The complex was ignited to copper oxide which was then dissolved in a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acid and the copper estimated iodometrically. Water content was determined by loss at 130°-140°. Nitrogen was determined by semi-micro combustion technique.

Physical measurements: Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr matrices. Electronic spectra in solution were recorded in Hilger-Waats Uvispek

spectrophotometer using 1 cm light path. Reflectance spectra were recorded by Zeiss PMQ II spectrophotometer. Magnetic moments were obtained as usual⁸. Conductance was measured at $10^{-3}M$ concentration in water.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of the mixed chelates: The copper(II) mixed chelates containing iminodiacetate ion and dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline have been obtained by two straight forward synthetic routes: (1) by feeding $[Cu(IDA)aq]$ with one mole of *o*-phenanthroline or dipyridyl; (2) by feeding $[Cu(o\text{-phen})aq]X_2$ or $[Cu(dipy)aq]X_2$ obtained *in situ* with one mole of iminodiacetic acid. The compound $[Cu(BigH)(IDA)(H_2O)]0.5H_2O$ was obtained by feeding the $IDA H_2$ in the equilibrium⁹:

or by feeding biguanide hydrochloride to a solution of $[Cu(IDA)aq]$.

Conductivity, Chromatographic behaviour and Magnetic moments: The complexes have non-electrolytic conductance in water (Table 2). These values rule out any alternative ionic formulations such as $[Cu(dipy)_2][Cu(IDA)_2]$ or $[Cu(o\text{-phen})_2][Cu(IDA)_2]$. They always exhibit a single spot on filter paper when developed in aqueous KCl-pyridine¹⁰. The magnetic moment values of copper(II) complexes are generally in the range 1.8 to 2.2 BM^{11,12}. The magnetic moment values of our complexes (Table 2) lie in the range 1.77 to 1.93 BM. Magnetic data do not reveal any special feature.

Thermogravimetric analysis: The thermogram of $[Cu(o\text{-phen})(IDA)(H_2O)]1.5H_2O$ was run from 30° to 600°. From 100° to 125° the compound loses some

water giving a loss ~8%. A stable product continues upto 155° whereafter further decomposition starts and ultimately it is converted to copper oxide at a temperature of 440°. The thermogram points distinctly to the fact that the entire water in the compound is not lost at 110°–125°, some still being held tenaciously. This indicates that some coordinated water is present in the compound. Prolonged heating at 130°–140°, however, removes all the water.

Infrared spectra: Iminodiacetic acid has some bands ~3077 and ~1709 cm^{-1} (Table 3) characteristic of the N–H and free carboxyl stretching frequencies respectively, comparable to those of ethylenediamine tetracetic acid¹³. The three mixed chelates have bands at 1650–1600 cm^{-1} characteristic of ionised and coordinated carboxyl band¹³. In the biguanide complex the coordinated carboxyl stretch overlaps C = N stretch of biguanide. Bis(biguanide) copper (II) alone has a C = N stretch at 1603 cm^{-1} . A band at ~1665 cm^{-1} has been regarded as the coordinated water vibration in copper(II) complex of 1-amidino-2-thiourea¹⁴. Such a band in the present mixed chelates cannot be identified independently because the COO⁻ and C = N stretches overwhelm this region. That the heterocycles are coordinated is revealed by the presence of some bands (Table 3) which are not present in $IDA H_2$ but are present both in the mixed chelates $[Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H_2O)]5H_2O$ and $[Cu(o\text{-phen})(IDA)(H_2O)]1.5H_2O$ and in $[Cu(o\text{-phen})Cl_2]$ or $[Cu(dipy)Cl_2]$.

Electronic spectra: The reflectance spectra (Table 4) of two of the mixed chelates $[Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H_2O)]5H_2O$ and $[Cu(o\text{-phen})(IDA)(H_2O)]1.5H_2O$ have broad single absorption bands at ~15 kK. These two complexes also show single band at ~15.1 kK in water. This indicates that the effective ligand field environment around the metal ion remains the

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION OF THE COPPER(II) MIXED CHELATES

Compound	Method	% Cu		% N		% H ₂ O	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
$[Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H_2O)]5H_2O$	A	13.8	13.8	9.1	8.9	23.5	23.4
	B	13.8	13.5	—	—	23.5	23.9
$[Cu(o\text{-phen})(IDA)(H_2O)]1.5H_2O$	A	15.1	14.9	10.0	10.2	10.7	10.4
	B	15.1	15.0	—	—	10.7	10.6
$[Cu(BigH)(IDA)(H_2O)]0.5H_2O$	A	19.7	19.2	25.1	25.6	8.4	8.1
	B	19.7	20.2	—	—	8.4	8.5

TABLE 2—CONDUCTIVITY AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES (METHOD A)

Compound	$\chi_{Meorr} \times 10^6$	T°K	μ_{eff}	Conductivity (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹) in water at 25°
$[Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H_2O)]5H_2O$	1291	303.0	1.77	~9
$[Cu(o\text{-phen})(IDA)(H_2O)]1.5H_2O$	1398	303.0	1.82	~8
$[Cu(BigH)(IDA)(H_2O)]0.5H_2O$	1637	304.5	1.93	~8

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRAL ASSIGNMENTS OF THE LIGANDS AND THE MIXED CHELATES (METHOD A)

Compound/ligand	dipy/o-phen	ν_{COOH} (uncoordinated)	ν_{COOH} (coordinated)	$\nu_{C=N}$
IDA H ₂	—	1709 m	—	—
[Cu(BigH) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	—	—	—	1603 m
[Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H ₂ O)]5H ₂ O	1163 m 735 m	—	1653 s 1626 m	—
[Cu(o-phen)(IDA)(H ₂ O)]1.5H ₂ O	1143 m 772 m	—	1653 sh, 1613 s	—
[Cu(BigH)(IDA)(H ₂ O)]0.5H ₂ O	—	—	1613 s	—

[Cu(dipy)Cl₂] have strong bands at 1440, 1167 and 730 cm⁻¹ and [Cu(o-phen)Cl₂] shows bands at 1420, 1195 and 735 cm⁻¹.
s = strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE MIXED CHELATES (METHODS A & B)

Compound	State	Colour	Absorption bands in kK	ϵ_{max}
[Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H ₂ O)]5H ₂ O	Water Reflectance	blue —	15.1 15.2	57 —
[Cu(o-phen)(IDA)(H ₂ O)]1.5H ₂ O	Water Reflectance	blue —	15.1—14.9 15.2	54 —
[Cu(BigH)(IDA)(H ₂ O)]0.5H ₂ O	Water	blue	13.8—13.5	95

same both in the solid state and the aqueous solution. This is consistent with our contention that one H₂O is coordinated to copper(II). It is also of interest to note that the absorption band at ~15 kK of [Cu(dipy)(IDA)(H₂O)]5H₂O and [Cu(o-phen)(IDA)(H₂O)]1.5H₂O shifts to ~13.6 kK in [Cu(BigH)(IDA)(H₂O)]0.5H₂O being in agreement with relative disposition of the three bidentate N-N donors in the spectrochemical series¹⁵. In the solid state our mixed chelates are not really five coordinate [CuN₃O₂]; instead these have distorted [CuN₃O₃] chromophore. Further we have observed no visual colour change on dehydration of these chelates. This would indicate that the chromophore [CuN₃O₃] is still retained through the iminodiacetate oxygen functioning as bridges between mixed chelate units giving either a dimeric or polymeric structure (compare Fig. 1 of reference 1). Since there is hardly any difference between the crystal field strength of similar bridging and terminal atoms¹⁶, no colour change is expected on dehydration.

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